

Oxidation Protection for C-C Composites: Inhibitor/Substrate Interaction

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ABSTRACT

Oxidation testing of the carbon-carbon specimens is performed as a function of time and temperature in order to isolate the contribution of the inhibitor. Mass loss and material property degradation are assessed with subsequent exploratory nondestructive testing of rheometry and piezoelectric ultrasonic composite oscillator (PUCOT) techniques. An analytical diffusion model is developed to predict composite degradation for given exposure conditions, and these results are compared with the experimental data generated.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber/carbon matrix (C-C) composites are one of the few structural materials that retain room temperature strength in inert environments up to 2000 °C [1]. However, these composites oxidize rapidly in oxygen rich environments at temperatures in excess of 450 °C. Thus, protecting the C-C from oxidation has become an important goal to achieve for many high temperature applications. This protection of carbon-carbon from oxidation has proceeded in complexity from a single layer external barrier coating to a complicated oxidation protection system (OPS) involving multi-layer external barrier coatings.

Sheehan [2] suggests that, in addition to resisting oxygen penetration, one of the most important criteria for selection of an acceptable external barrier coating is matching the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) with the composite, which leads to the selection of silicon carbide and silicon nitride as two obvious choices. However, boron carbide is added as an intermediate layer due to increased wetting characteristics with carbon [3] and to avoid an adverse reaction of silicon with carbon at elevated temperatures, 1500 °C and above [2]. Regardless of attempts to match CTE of the coatings and the composite, cracks continue to form in the coatings with changes in temperature.

Inhibitor particles in an OPS react with oxygen that penetrates the cracks in external barrier coatings to form a liquid phase which serves as an internal sealant to provide extended oxidation protection [4]. Common inhibitor materials include boron, boron carbide, and silicon carbide. The carbon-carbon composite examined in this research is a HITCO, 2-D, eight harness satin weave carbon-carbon laminate with boron carbide (B_4C) inhibitor particles and multi-layer silicon carbide (SiC) coating.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

As previously mentioned, oxidation of carbon-carbon composites has rarely been related in any form other than mass loss. For this reason it is desirable to experimentally demonstrate and document the material property degradation as a function of oxidation. Experimental techniques of rheometry and PUCOT testing will be used to relate elastic moduli to oxidation exposure.

Oxidation experiments are performed in two different ways; namely at constant temperature and at cyclic temperature. Constant temperature tests provide valuable data for future modeling by isolating the importance of a single temperature on the length of exposure. The "temperature cycling" approach examines the importance of fatigue crack formation due to expansion and contraction. The oxidation of the inhibitor particles has been found to occur at around 900 °C, and existing analytical models establish a transition from reaction control oxidation rate to diffusion controlled rate at approximately 800 °C. Therefore, temperatures will vary from 700 - 1050 °C in order to capture these effects, as well as exposing the specimens to typical temperature ranges of carbon/carbon mission cycling.

Groups of four specimens are oxidized at four different temperatures of 700, 850, 950, and 1050 °C by placing all specimens in the furnace at one time and removing one specimen every forty five minutes within each temperature range. In addition, one group of eight specimens follows a temperature cycle while removing one specimen every thirty minutes. The goal of this temperature cycle is to start at the temperature of 700 °C, increase to 950 °C, decrease to 850 °C, and finally increase to 1050 °C. The initial size of the specimens is approximately 4 mm thick, 11.5 mm wide, and 37.2 mm long, with coating on the front and back sides only.

RHEOMETRY

Once oxidation is accomplished and mass loss data is recorded, nondestructive evaluation is performed. A servo motor is used to apply an oscillatory strain input to the specimen in the RMS rheometry equipment. The percent strain input is measured as a given amplitude of rotation on the bottom platen, and is not the actual percent strain of the specimen. The strain input travels along the length of the specimen and registers an output on the transducer. For the torsional dynamic mechanical analysis used in this investigation, a sinusoidal strain input is applied to the test specimens. The transducer output is a measure of the phase lag (δ) between the input strain and the stress recorded by the transducer. For a purely elastic material δ equals 0 degrees, while for a purely viscoelastic material, δ equals 90 degrees. In actuality, the phase angle lies between purely elastic and purely viscoelastic, and thus in the carbon/carbon specimens the phase angle is very small due to its highly brittle-elastic behavior. In the torsional dynamic mechanical test the input strain and output stress are related by the complex storage and loss modulus terms, G' and G'' respectively. Given these definitions the phase angle is expressed simply as a ratio of G' and G'' ,

$$\tan \delta = \frac{G''}{G'}$$

And, as the phase angle approaches 0 degrees, the storage modulus approaches the elastic modulus.

Rheometry testing is performed on unoxidized as well as oxidized specimens at room temperature to estimate the shear modulus. During the tests the angular frequency is held constant at 10 radians per second while the strain is varied. This strain sweep produces a plot of the storage and loss modulus.

PUCOT

A second nondestructive technique, the piezoelectric ultrasonic composite oscillator technique (PUCOT) offers a means of estimating the axial modulus of specimens using piezoelectric crystal vibrations. The first step, while the specimen is unattached to the crystal, involves supplying a small voltage to the gauge crystal, and recording an output voltage and frequency of vibration from the drive crystal. Then the specimen is bonded to the crystals and the same procedure is repeated. Finally, by relating the frequencies and masses of the system with and without the specimen, the frequency of the specimen is calculated, and this frequency along with the length and the density can be used to estimate the axial modulus.

The primary challenge in PUCOT testing is the selection of the proper frequency crystals. Many iterative steps are taken until the frequency produced in the specimen matches that of the crystals. This efficiency of vibration is an indicator of a valid test. The trial tests of carbon-carbon defined the need to account for area of contact with the crystals, as the small size of the crystals, 3mm square, did not provide valuable data. The contact area problem is corrected with the addition of a quartz rod, that is usually used for high temperature testing, which is tuned by varying its length to vibrate at the same frequency as the piezoelectric crystals.

DIFFUSION MODEL

Since the test specimens are coated on front and back surfaces with silicon carbide coating, the model will apply one dimensional analysis. It has already been determined that diffusion control as the rate limiting step of the oxidation process begins at approximately 800 °C. Therefore, the temperature range selected for analytical modeling is above 800 °C. During oxidation pores are created in the C-C when fibers preferentially oxidize along their length. Therefore, as demonstrated in Figure 1, the rate of diffusion will depend on whether oxygen is transferring through an open pore, an inhibitor filled pore, or matrix. The analytical model is based on an ash model by Nam and Seferis [5]. Herein the ash layer is treated as the graphitized region.

Several critical assumptions are made for this analytical model. Through the thickness, z-direction, oxidation is taken to be uniform. Second, a line of symmetry is assumed to exist that will have similar components and levels of oxidation on either side of the line. The diffusivity of oxygen through the porous oxidized matrix is assumed to resemble the diffusivity of oxygen in air. The concentration of oxygen is given by the concentration of oxygen in ambient air. Next, the pores opening in the fiber bundles are assumed to be represented by a circular cross section with effective area equivalent to the original area of the pores. The inhibitor content along any given layer of oxidation is assumed to be constant at fifteen percent. Finally, the pore content of the exposed edge is assumed to be eighty percent.

Figure 1. Schematic of the diffusion model

The equation for calculating mass loss per unit area is virtually identical for the three regions of the analytical model. For open pores and closed pores the weight loss per unit area is given by

$$q_c = \left(\frac{8\rho_d C_{O_2} D}{\beta} \right)^{0.5} t^{0.5}$$

where ρ_d is the density of the composite, C_{O_2} is the concentration of oxygen in the air, D is the diffusivity of oxygen for the appropriate situation (open or closed pore, ash layer) adjusted for the size of the pore, β is the gram moles of oxygen consumed per gram of composite mass loss obtained from the chemical equations of the oxidation, and t is the time of oxidation. The temperature of the oxidation is carried in the above equation by the diffusivity term and the oxygen concentration term. Increasing the temperature increases both these terms. For the case of the ash layer the only change in the above equation is subtracting the density of the ash layer from the density of the composite giving

$$q_c = \left(\frac{8(\rho_d - \rho_o) C_{O_2} D}{\beta} \right)^{0.5} t^{0.5}$$

where ρ_o is the density of this layer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental data is analyzed to reveal trends that support the assumptions made in the diffusion model. Observation of oxidation specimens is initially performed using optical and SEM microscopy. Specimens evaluated under the optical microscope immediately after oxidation reveal that the inhibitor material has turned into a highly viscous glass that flows towards the outside of the specimen to seal forming cracks. Obviously, due to the large porosity of oxidized edges, the inhibitor can not fill every pore or crack. SEM photographs taken after the specimen has cooled can not accurately capture the inhibitor effect because the

inhibitor has solidified and reacted with ambient humidity to disappear. However, the SEM photography reveals definite initiation and preferential oxidation along fiber bundles. Thus, as oxidation progresses the exposed edges of the specimens are opening pores where fiber bundles have reacted with oxygen. These opening pores result in the largest portion of the mass loss.

MASS LOSS

The percent mass loss data is important for comparison with the analytical model. The data taken is from the isothermal and temperature cycling conditions. Figure 2 shows constant temperature data as solid lines and temperature cycling data as a dotted line. Each point on the plot represents a single specimen oxidized for a given length of time.

Figure 2. Isothermal and temperature cycling mass loss data

The isothermal data demonstrates an important transition in the controlling oxidation mechanism from surface reaction to diffusion dominance occurring between the 700 °C and the 1050 °C data. Two factors support this conclusion. First, the significant rise in amount of mass loss between the 700 °C and the 850 °C data indicates that the process must be changing. And, secondly, the growing nonlinearity of the curve fit in the data at higher temperatures reveals a change in the mechanism of oxidation control. This transition is important because it verifies that diffusion should be the dominant process in the analytical model.

SHEAR MODULUS DEGRADATION

A typical rheometry strain sweep is used to give an estimate of shear modulus, which, for carbon-carbon, should be essentially constant across all frequencies. However, in the typical curves, there is a slight decrease in the complex moduli as the rotation level is increased. Two observations serve as indicators that the rheometry test is an accurate measure of the shear modulus response of the carbon-carbon material. The first indicator is the phase lag angle (ratio of the storage and loss modulus). Examining typical values for storage and loss modulus shows a phase lag of 2-4 degrees. This small phase lag indicates a very elastic response that would be expected from the high stiffness carbon-carbon material. Secondly, due to this small phase lag angle, the storage modulus is an accurate representation of the

material shear modulus. For example, a strain sweep of an unoxidized specimen gives an estimated shear modulus of 5 GPa (0.725 Msi) which corresponds closely with data obtained from mechanical testing.

Figure 3. Exposure time effect on storage modulus at 950 °C

The primary purpose of the rheometry testing is to nondestructively relate oxidation exposure to shear modulus degradation. Figure 3 shows the storage modulus curves for four specimens oxidized at 950 °C for different lengths of time. The shear modulus degradation is evident by the shift downward of each curve as the oxidation exposure time increases. Importantly, at approximately two hours the shear modulus degradation seems to increase. Finally, for comparison purposes, Figure 4 shows a plot of storage modulus for all temperature and time ranges. One data point for each specimen is obtained by averaging the essentially constant storage modulus values.

Figure 4. Storage modulus from rheometry testing for all time and temperature ranges

The quick degradation of properties as the temperature is increased from 700 °C to 850 °C is significant. This large difference in property degradation, similar to the mass loss results, indicates the switch from surface reaction to diffusion dominance of the oxidation process. Thus, the rheometry results also support the assumption of diffusion control in the analytical

model. Also, the shear modulus values appear to be converging at extended oxidation times. Not a surprising result since shear modulus is a matrix dominant response.

AXIAL MODULUS DEGRADATION

The axial modulus degradation is obtained using the PUCOT technique. Figure 5 is a plot of recorded axial modulus for each specimen. The points are connected to estimate the slope of the degradation. However, the curve fit is a simple connecting of the data points, so is not necessarily a good scientific estimation. The modulus degradation from the PUCOT test shows a logical progression. The modulus decreases more quickly with increasing exposure time and increasing exposure temperature. Similar to shear modulus degradation, the largest decrease in axial modulus occurs after approximately two hours of oxidation.

Figure 5. Axial modulus degradation from PUCOT testing

ANALYTICAL COMPARISON

The easiest comparison of the effectiveness of the diffusion model at predicting oxidation is to examine experimental mass loss data. The analytical model agrees quite well with experimental data as shown in Figure 6. For smaller exposure times the diffusion model overestimates the amount of mass loss. This is easily explained by noticing that the experimental data points are for specimens placed in the oven after it is heated to a specified temperature. Therefore, while the model assumes diffusion to begin immediately, the actual diffusion does not begin until the specimens have time to reach an elevated temperature. Thus, the model should overestimate the initial mass loss.

The diffusion model also appears to begin underestimating the mass loss after approximately two hours of oxidation. Several reasons could exist for this underestimation. As discussed previously the many assumptions of the analytical model make it subject to certain errors. By varying the inhibitor content, the porosity, and the diffusivity of oxygen in the model, it can be shown that the experimental results are well within satisfactorily predicted range. A more likely explanation, however, would be the loss in effectiveness of the inhibitor material. Experimental results previously discussed verify that the inhibitor could be losing effectiveness after approximately two hours of oxidation for these particular specimens.

Figure 6. Comparison of diffusion model with experimental mass loss

CONCLUSION

Nondestructive techniques of rheometry and PUCOT are used to obtain the shear and axial modulus degradation of a carbon-carbon composite after oxidation. Evaluation of the experimental data demonstrates a period of effectiveness of the inhibitor particles for about two hours for these particular specimens. A diffusion model accurately predicts the mass loss of the specimens, and similarly could predict area loss as well. Thus, future elevated temperature mechanical testing of the material could be corrected for area change as the test progresses. The nondestructive testing techniques and the diffusion model can successfully trace the material property change of inhibited carbon-carbon composite as oxidation progresses.

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